

IMPROVED ACCESSIBILITY OF BUS RAPID TRANSIT FOR SCHOOL-GOING CHILDREN: A CASE OF BUS RAPID TRANSIT PHASE 1 IN DAR ES SALAAM CITY, TANZANIA

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ABSTRACT

In highly urbanizing cities, public transport is the main mode of transport. However, it is faced with many challenges of which Bus Rapid Transit (BRT) was introduced to address them. Despite of BRT introduction in the African developing countries, its accessibility to school-going children remains a challenge. Therefore, the objective of this study was to fill the knowledge gap of school-going children accessibility to BRT stations, operational challenges and safety issues. A mixed-method approach was employed in this study, combining both qualitative and quantitative data collection techniques. The sample size was 80 respondents. Open Data Kite (ODK) compatible with android phones was used for data collection and analysis. Findings of the study shows that there are no favorable conditions for school-going children while using BRT services. The key issues are three. Firstly, accessibility of BRT stations in-terms of distance and time; secondly, operational challenges in-terms of insufficient number of

buses dedicated for school-going children, ticketing problems and passengers' overcrowding; and thirdly, safety issues. It is concluded that BRT services have improved transportation for school-going children. However, it is recommended for further improvements in-terms of providing subsidy for school-going children instead of providing dedicated buses for them, increasing the number of buses and improved accessibility while boarding the BRT stations and buses.

Keywords: School-going children, public transport, and bus rapid transit

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1. Background Information

Public Transport provides a shared passenger transport for the general public (Basso, Navarro, & Silva, 2021; Newman & Kenworkthy, 1999). Wijaya (2009) defined public transport as a form of travel offered locally to enable movement of people to travel together along the designed routes and charges a fee for each trip. Also, Mchome (2021) defined public transport as a shared passenger transport which is available for use by the general public, operated on an established route and charges a fixed fare for each trip. Since its discovery in the 1960s, public transport has been playing a crucial role in improving the quality of life by providing safe, efficient, and economical transport services (Mchome & Nzoya, 2023).

There are different means of public transport. The common ones include buses, trolleybuses, coaches, trams, metro, bahn, trains, light rail transit, monorail, commuter rail, mass rapid transit, bus rapid transit, ferries and domestic aircraft (Mchome, 2021). This study focusses on bus rapid transit.

African developing countries experience unique challenges in public transport caused by rapid urban population increase, inadequate and poor road infrastructure, increased use of private vehicles, traffic congestion, and insufficient and ineffective public transport operation systems (Iles, 2005; Mchome & Nzoya, 2023; Nzoya & Kazaura, 2024). For instance, Kaba (2020) asserts that African countries have a massive increase in population, relative to other parts of the world, rapidly increasing from 228.7 million in 1950 to over 1.341 billion in 2020.

This implies a high demand for public transport. Furthermore, Msigwa (2013) stated that public transport in Dar es Salaam City is used by 61% of all commuters. Moreover, Kaba (2020) showed that among the continents of the world, African countries have the highest proportions of under age 15 or a median age of 20 years or less, which is the age range of school-going children. This also implies the increase in transport demand, mostly for school-going children to facilitate their daily movements, to and from the schools.

Bus Rapid Transit (BRT) is among the most commonly used public transport by school-going children. BRT is a flexible, rubber-tired form of rapid transit that combines stations, vehicles, services, running ways, and information technologies into an integrated system with a strong identity (Hidalgo, 2011; Mchome, 2021). The complete BRT system offers fast, comfortable, and low-cost urban mobility which favors school-going children. BRT system is an evolution of bus priority measures, such as designated busways and bus lanes (Levinson, et al., 2003). The United States was the first beneficiary of BRT in 1966 which then gained popularity in Latin America after the successful upgrade of bus ways in Curitiba, Brazil in 1982 (Lindau, Hidalgo, & Facchini, 2010). It was then adopted in Quito, Bogota, Mexico, Beijing, Jakarta, Los Angeles, Istanbul, and Guangzhou cities where the idea was made more attractive and acceptable throughout the world. Reaching January 2011, there were about 118 cities with BRT (Hildago, 2011). In Dar es Salaam city, BRT was introduced in 2016 and it accommodates school-going children (Mchome, 2021).

School-going children access BRT in many countries primarily by walking or cycling to the nearby stations from the residential areas and schools. Furthermore, many cities offer discounted bus fares or free rides for school-going children (Botzoris et al, 2016; Cervero, 2005; Gutiérrez, 2013; Hidalgo & Gutiérrez, 2013; Rodríguez & Targa, 2004).

Despite of BRT accommodation of school-going children, still its accessibility in developing countries, including Tanzania remains a riddle. Therefore, this study explores the challenges faced by school-going children while accessing BRT services. The study was guided by the following specific objectives;

1. To explore convenience challenges of BRT stations by school-going children.
2. To examine operational challenges of BRT services to school-going children.
3. To identify safety challenges of BRT services to school-going children.

2. Research Methodology

Given the multifaceted nature of the research topic, the methodology used combined qualitative and quantitative approaches to ensure a comprehensive analysis of the BRT challenges to school-going children. This mixed-methods approach enabled the collection of both numerical data to quantify patterns and detailed qualitative insights to capture perceptions and the non-numeric data in general. Structured questionnaires, open-ended questions and surveys were used for data collection. The study opted for a case study approach whereby BRT Phase I in Dar es Salaam city was selected as the case study. According to Kothari (2004), the case study method is a widely used approach that involves meticulous and comprehensive observation of a particular phenomenon. In the context of this research, the case study approach defined the study's focus.

The sample size was 80 respondents that was established by using the mathematical formula $(n) = N \div [1 + N(e^2)]$ (Kihale, 2011); whereby, n = sample size, N =study population, and e =confidence level (0.05). The study population (N) was the total BRT commuters (300,000 people) and the average household size was 5 people. Therefore, the sample size;

$$(n) = N \div [1 + N(e^2)]$$

$$(n) = 300,000 \div [1 + 300,000(0.05^2)] = 399.4673768 \div 5$$

$$(n) = 80 \text{ respondents.}$$

Open Data Kite (ODK) compatible with android phones was used for data collection. The same was applied for data analysis of which ODK server (Kobo Toolbox) was used to download the collected data in excel format that was then transformed to SPSS to generate tables and figures.

3. Research Findings and Discussions

3.1 Convenience of BRT Stations by School-Going Children

The study assumed that after implementation of BRT Phase I, public transport for school-going children was improved. The system connects residential areas with schools, ensuring efficient and predictable transportation for school-going children. The use of dedicated bus lanes and traffic management measures allowed for faster and more efficient services, and minimizing travel time to commuters including school-going children. Two parameters, namely distance and time were used to evaluate convenience of BRT stations for school-going children.

Distance

The study analyzed the distance of the existing schools along the BRT Phase I route to the nearest BRT stations. Figure 1 shows that 46% of all schools (125 out of 269 schools) are located within 400m from the nearest BRT stations. On the other hand, 54% (144 out 269 schools) are located more than 400m away from the nearest BRT stations.

Transit Oriented Development (TOD) that is mostly used in urban planning recommends 300-400m walking distance from home/school to destinations (Ali, 2014) that is BRT stations in this context. The fieldwork findings show that 46% of the schools are located within the recommendable walking distance of 400m while the remaining 54% are located more than 400m walking distance from the BRT stations. Longer distances can cause several difficulties for school-going children when accessing BRT stations. Firstly, the physical exhaustions due to long walking distances, especially for younger school-going children can cause them to be tired and adversely affect their concentration in schools. This can be worsened in bad weather conditions, such as extreme heat, rain, or cold. Secondly, this exposes school-going children to more risks including safety.

Figure 1: Distance from the Schools to the Nearest BRT Stations

Source: Fieldwork, 2024

Time

TOD recommends 5 to 10 minutes walking time from home/school to destinations (Ali, 2014) that is BRT stations in this context. The fieldwork findings (Figure 2) shows that majority of the school-going children (72%) spend more than 10 minutes from home to BRT stations by walking. On the other hand, the BRT buses dedicated for school-going children start to pick-up school-going children from 06:30 to 07:30 hours in the morning, but due to distance majority of the school-going children come-up late and miss the service on-time. Similarly, this applies to the time they spend walking back from school to the BRT stations in the evening.

Figure 2: Walking time of the school-going children from home/school to BRT stations

Source: Fieldwork, 2024

It is important to note that efficiency of the BRT service is to be easily accessible by the commuters including school-going children. As explained by Hidalgo & Gutiérrez (2013), it was underscored that connection of the schools and residential houses to the BRT stations is the key factor for effective movement of school-going children.

3.2 BRT Services for School-going Children

The study identified various operational challenges of BRT services that affects the school-going children. The BRT challenges were studied in three categories, namely; availability of BRT buses, ticketing and passengers overcrowding.

Availability of BRT Buses

Many studies including Mchome and Nzoya (2023) explain deficit of BRT buses to be among the general challenges facing BRT services in Dar es Salaam City. Since Phase 1 BRT inception in 2016, the BRT Service provider had managed to purchase a total of 210 Golden Dragon buses out of 500 required buses of which 211 are articulated (trunk) buses (18 metre long) and 289 are rigid (feeder) buses (12 metre long). This means only 42% of the buses have been purchased. Furthermore, out of 210 buses, 60 buses were not operating due to mechanical breakdowns making a total fleet of 150 buses. This implies that there is still an unmet demand for more than 290 buses. From the estimated 300,000 BRT commuters per day, the available number of BRT buses are very few that also affects their availability for school-going children.

From 2019, DART dedicated four (4) BRT buses for school-going children (each with capacity of 160 passengers) during the peak hours. The buses start to pick-up school-going children from 6:30 to 7.30 am and then from 4:30 to 6:30 pm covering the routes from Gerezani to Kimara, and Kivukoni to Kimara (2 buses for each route). However, the provided number of BRT buses are very few. As a result, school-going children end up using normal buses meant for regular passengers that are not easily accessed during the morning and evening peak hours. This shows the continuing challenge for school-going children during the peak hours.

In other countries, subsidies were used for facilitation of school-going children instead of dedicating a special bus for them. For instance, in Greece, the government offers special subsidy strategies for school-going children, making the public transport, mainly BRT system affordable for them. India made a step ahead of which a significant proportion of school trips are made using motorized transport, with distance to school being a major determinant of transport mode (Tetali et al., 2016). Furthermore, the Central Regions signed public service contracts with private companies to serve school-going children who are living over 1.2 km away from their schools (Botzoris et al, 2016). Also in Colombia, the government offers a special subsidy program for school-going children, making the BRT system affordable for school-going children (Cervero, 2005).

Rodríguez & Targa (2004) explains that the urban planning authority in Bogota, Colombia includes pedestrian walkways and cycling lanes connected to the BRT stations making it easier for school-going children to reach the stations safely. Furthermore, feeder buses connects to BRT stations and BRT terminals that enables school-going children connect their trips from home to school more easily (Hidalgo & Gutiérrez, 2013).

Ticketing Challenges

Ticketing for school-going children has been observed to be another challenge in BRT operations. Ticketing for school-going children cost only T.Shs. 200/=. The study revealed that majority of the BRT stations demand the student to have exactly T.Shs 200/=. If not, they are rejected and being required to look for a change. This is particularly problematic during the peak hours (morning and evening hours). One of the interviewed school-going-children had this to say;

"When we give ticket sellers more than T.Shs 200/=:, they tell us to find our own change and sometimes make us wait for a long time until they find change "

Also, the study observed unfair treatment of the school-going children while buying tickets. The fieldwork observed two queues for buying tickets; one for special group like women, and disabled and another for ordinary passengers. Despite that many literatures consider school-going children as special group; they are not given priority of being accommodated at the dedicated line for special groups. One of the interviewed school-going children had this to say;

"When we line up to buy tickets and get onboard, we school-going children are placed by security guards in the line for ordinary passengers "

Ticketing challenges might have negative impacts to school-going children. The above findings imply that school-going children are at high risk of missing morning sessions due to difficulties of obtaining tickets related with cash and long queue.

Passengers overcrowding

Passengers overcrowding in the BRT buses especially during the peak hours (morning and evening) is a prominent challenge in Dar es Salaam City. According to a DART operator: articulated (trunk) busses (18 metre long) are designed to carry about 160 passengers (120 standing and 40 seating passengers) while rigid (feeder) buses (12 metre long) are designed to carry about 80 passengers. However, during peak hours, articulated buses were observed to carry about 300 passengers squeezed in the bus compared to their design capacity of 160 passengers while rigid (feeder) buses were observed to carry about 150 passengers squeezed in the bus compared to their design capacity of 80 passengers.

This is a challenge to school-going children, who often struggle to compete with other passengers for space and may experience being trampled, pushed, or even pickpocketed. About 68% of the school-going children explained overcrowding in the BRT buses to occur mostly

on Mondays while 32% explained overcrowding to be a daily problem. This also makes school-going children to wait a little bit longer before embarking into the buses at the BRT stations.

Due to passengers overcrowding, the study revealed that school-going children face difficulties during embarking and disembarking the BRT buses during the peak hours (morning and evening hours). During the struggle to get in and out of the buses, some school-going children are injured. Consequently, those who cannot struggle have to take more waiting time before boarding a bus and reach home very late.

3.3 Safety Challenges of BRT Services to School-going Children

The study discusses safety issues of school-going children while using BRT in four categories: safety when crossing the road to/from the BRT stations; safety in the BRT stations and terminals; safety when boarding the BRT buses; and; safety inside the BRT buses.

Safety when crossing the road to BRT stations/terminals

The findings show that 95% of the interviewed respondents said that school-going children are safe while crossing the roads to/from the BRT stations and terminals. This was due to presence of road signs and markings, traffic lights and pedestrian bridges. Additionally, road signs and markings for pedestrian crosses are strictly adhered to by drivers, especially when it comes to allow crossing of the school-going children. However, 5% of the respondents explained that it is not safe for the school-going children while crossing the roads from/to the BRT stations due to negligence of the motorcycle riders.

Safety in the BRT stations and terminals

The study shows that 73% of the interviewed respondents explained that it is safe for school-going children inside the BRT stations and terminals. Through field survey, security guards were observed in all BRT stations and terminals to ensure safety and security for all BRT passengers, including school-going children. However, the remaining 27% of the respondents explained that safety is an issue for school-going children inside the BRT stations and terminals during the peak hours (morning and evening hours) due to overcrowding of passengers.

Safety when boarding the BRT buses

The study shows that 82% of the interviewed respondents explained that BRT stations are not safe for school-going children where they have to struggle and compete with adult passengers boarding the BRT buses. In these occasions, school-going children are pushed by adult passengers and sometimes drop their belongings such as shoes, books and textbooks. Sometimes during the struggle school-going children are injured. Lindén, Kanyama & Kanyama (2006) also observed safety issues for school-going children in public transport.

However, the situation is not the same in the BRT terminals of Kivukoni, Gerezani, Morocco and Kimara where safety issues are secured. In this case, both adult passengers and school-going children are safe as they line-up when boarding the BRT buses.

Safety in the BRT buses

The study revealed that school-going children are not safe in the BRT buses during the morning and evening peak hours when they travel to/from the schools. One of the interviewed school-going children had this to say;

“It is not safe inside the BRT buses during the morning and evening hours due to high congestion of passengers. Some of the adults squeeze us to the extent that there is no space even to move a foot”

4. Conclusion and Recommendations

It is concluded that tremendous endeavors have been done for improvement of BRT services for school going children. However, findings on the accessibility of BRT stations and terminals by school-going children in-terms of walking distance and time shows that they are not accessible. Also, findings on availability of BRT buses for school-going children is a challenge in-terms of insufficient number of buses, ticketing problems and passengers’ overcrowding. Furthermore, findings on safety and security of school-going children when boarding the buses in the BRT stations and inside the buses is a big problem during the peak hours.

It is therefore, recommended that parents and guardians should take their responsibilities to escort and pick-up school-going children to and from the BRT stations. It is also recommended that the authorities governing the BRT operations in urban areas should consider the issue of subsidy instead of providing BRT buses for school-going children, the former proved to be more efficient with experience from other countries. Apart from increasing the number of buses, it is also recommended to line-up when boarding the BRT buses of which a separate line should be provided for special group to include school-going children, elderly and women.

Furthermore, it is recommended to improve feeder routes to the BRT stations and terminals so-as-to reduce walking distance of the school-going children. Findings show that the majority of the schools and residential houses are located more than the recommended 400m and 10 minutes walking distance to/from the BRT stations that expose school-going children

to the risks of safety, physical exhaustions and adverse weather conditions such as extreme heat and rain.

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